

Impulsivity, Psychopathy, and the Dark Triad: A Czech Validation of the Dirty Dozen Scale

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Abstract

Background: The dark triad concept suggests dark personality traits share a common core. Having reliable measurement tools is essential to test this claim. Concerns exist about the widely used Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (DTDD) tool, specifically regarding its ability to fully assess psychopathy. This study aims to adapt the DTDD for a Czech population and to enhance the psychopathy subscale by adding additional items. Examining the scale's functioning in different linguistic and cultural contexts is crucial for ensuring its validity beyond the populations in which it was originally developed, and the Czech sample provides an opportunity to assess the stability of the DTDD in a less frequently studied setting.

Methods: This study ($n = 6.715$, Mean Age = 36.14, SD = 14.72, Females: 65.5%) collected data from four online surveys in a Czech population. In addition to socio-demographic characteristics, we measured empathy, the Dark Triad (Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy), self-esteem, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Neuroticism.

Results: Results supported the original 12-item DTDD's three-factor structure (CFI = 0.942; TLI = 0.925; RMSEA = 0.062; SRMR = 0.055), showing good internal consistency for the general Dark Triad factor (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.85$ and McDonald's $\omega = 0.89$). A 14-item DTDD version with additional items demonstrated slightly lower fit (CFI = 0.93; TLI = 0.912; RMSEA = 0.063; SRMR = 0.062) and comparable internal consistency to the 12-item version. The 12-

item version was invariant between genders, with males scoring higher. Narcissism correlated negatively with Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, and self-esteem, and positively with Neuroticism. Machiavellianism and psychopathy were negatively associated with empathy, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness, and positively with Neuroticism.

Conclusions: This research confirms the 12-item DTDD scale's validity in the Czech population.

Keywords: DTDD, Dark Triad, psychopathy, narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychometrics, measurement

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Introduction

The Dark Triad personality, i.e., Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy, have received significant research attention in recent years. The focus on these traits stems from their harmful psychosocial effects that affect both the individuals themselves and the people around them [1–3]. These dark personality traits largely overlap [4, 5], but still represent distinct constructs. Some researchers, however, question the distinctiveness of Machiavellianism from psychopathy, pointing to significant empirical overlap between the two traits and suggesting that their differentiation may be less clear-cut [6–8]. Some other research suggests that the similarities between dark traits such as narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy can be attributed to a common dispositional core, referred to as the dark personality factor (D). This concept involves a general tendency to maximize one's individual utility accompanied by beliefs that serve as justifications for such behavior [9, 10].

Machiavellianism is characterised by manipulative tendencies, a pragmatic conception of morality or contempt for it, and a focus on self-interest and personal gain [11, 12]. Psychopathy is predominantly characterised by interpersonal and affective traits, such as low empathy [4, 12] and reduced ability or even a complete inability to feel remorse [12]. However, research on psychopathy distinguishes between interpersonal-affective traits and behavioral tendencies, with

the latter encompassing impulsivity and antisocial behavior as key components [13, 14]. Factor-analytic studies, including those using Hare's Psychopathy Checklist-Revised (PCL-R) [15], consistently demonstrate that impulsivity loads strongly on the so-called "lifestyle" factor of psychopathy [17, 18]. Additionally, analyses of the Psychopathic Personality Inventory (PPI) have identified impulsivity as part of a broader construct of "Self-Centered Impulsivity," which correlates with externalizing behaviors such as aggression and risk-taking [19]. However, some researchers, such as Poythress and Hall [20], have argued against the inclusion of impulsivity as a core feature of psychopathy, suggesting that it may be more characteristic of general externalizing tendencies rather than a defining element of the construct itself. Narcissism includes elements of grandiosity, egoism, and a sense of superiority [4], vanity satisfaction, and the need for admiration and validation [12]. Paulhus and Williams [21] introduced the idea that these three dark personality traits have a common core in which they empirically intersect. The empirical overlap of the Dark Triad has been explored primarily through common correlates with the Big Five personality traits [22–24]. These studies indicated that the unifying feature of the three "dark" personality dimensions is low Agreeableness. Besides that, Machiavellianism and psychopathy are associated with low Conscientiousness [22, 23] and Machiavellianism also with high Neuroticism [25, 26].

The Dark Triad itself can be assessed by two established measures: the Short Dark Triad (SD3; [27]) and the Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (DTDD; [28]) scales. The SD3 contains 27 items,

whereas the DTDD contains 12 items measuring the same traits. In recent years, a number of studies have been published comparing these two measurement methods in terms of convergent, discriminant, and criterion validity [1, 2, 29]. Criterion validity was supported for both measures across studies [1, 2, 29], however, there are some differences in other aspects. According to Maples and his colleagues [29], on the one hand, the SD3 measure is more consistent, but on the other hand, the DTDD is better able to capture vulnerable features of narcissism. At the same time, [30] noted that the brief measure of the Dark Triad offered by the DTDD may fail to capture some aspects of psychopathy. For instance, the DTDD scale does not include items to capture impulsivity and antisocial behavior in the psychopathy subscale.

Although impulsivity and antisocial behavior are recognized as important aspects of the lifestyle/antisocial factor in psychopathy [13, 14, 31] their absence in the DTDD scale may limit the assessment of psychopathy's multifaceted nature. The brevity of the scale could further restrict its ability to capture specific nuances of psychopathic traits, particularly those linked to risky behaviors. These features of psychopathy are manifested primarily in lifestyle - people with psychopathic traits are prone to experiencing boredom, constantly seek new stimuli, do not have many long-term goals, etc. [3, 15]. Moreover, these people also tend to have a distorted perception of risk and conventional moral values. Thus, psychopathic traits are associated with a higher tendency to engage in risks that violate conventional morals [31]. High levels of these traits are associated with risky behaviors [3] such as substance abuse [31–34] or risky sexual

behavior [31, 32, 35, 36]. Some studies have also confirmed a direct relationship between risk behavior and the whole dark triad [3, 37–39].

Although the original DTDD construct omitted impulsivity in favor of cynicism, its role in psychopathy is debated rather than universally recognized as central. In Hare's model, impulsivity belongs to Factor 2 and reflects a broader lifestyle/behavioral pattern often seen in criminal contexts [16], and Lykken [40] links it mainly to secondary psychopathy. However, other frameworks, such as Patrick's Triarchic Psychopathy Model [41], identify disinhibition (problems of impulse control) as one of three core components. Given that cynicism tends to overlap with Machiavellianism, as suggested by the results of factor analyses showing its weak saturation with the general factor of psychopathy [42]. Thus, the inclusion of items specifically measuring impulsivity and antisocial behavior could improve the DTDD's predictive validity for health-risk behaviors. At the same time, adding impulsivity and antisocial behavior could help to better distinguish psychopathy from Machiavellianism. Given that the SD3 psychopathy scale has demonstrated strong associations with externalizing behavior, risk-taking, and aggression [43, 44], the inclusion of its validated items could increase the predictive power of the DTDD while maintaining its parsimony.

To address the limitations of this widely used instrument for assessing the Dark Triad, the aim of this study is to validate the DTDD scale in the Czech population and to evaluate whether

adding items assessing impulsivity and antisocial behavior would increase the predictive validity of the psychopathy subscale and consequently lead to higher construct validity and to better differentiate psychopathy from other constructs of the Dark Triad. The validity of the DTDD will be evaluated by examining associations with other constructs to which the DTDD should be related, such as self-esteem, empathy, or the Big Five personality traits.

Based on previous research and the theoretical framework of the Dark Triad, we propose the following hypotheses: H1: Narcissism is positively associated with self-esteem. H2: Psychopathy (H2a) and machiavellism (H2b) are associated with Neuroticism. H3: The three-dimensional model has an adequate fit with the data. H4: Males reach higher scores in Machiavellianism (H4a), psychopathy (H4b), and narcissism (H4c) as compared with females. H5: Narcissism is not associated with Neuroticism (H5a) and Conscientiousness (H5b). H6: Agreeableness is negatively associated with narcissism (H6a), Machiavellianism (H6b), and psychopathy (H6c). H7: Conscientiousness is negatively associated with Machiavellianism (H7a), and psychopathy (H7b). H8: Empathy is negatively associated with narcissism (H8a), Machiavellianism (H8b), and psychopathy (H8c). The pre-registered proposal still contained the hypothesis: "DTDD composite score is positively associated with narcissism, Machiavellism, and psychopathy". This hypothesis was removed during the peer review process because it is not worth testing due to its tautological nature.

These hypotheses will guide the evaluation of the DTDD scale's construct validity and the potential benefit of additional items in improving the psychopathy subscale's predictive power.

Methods

Data from four different samples were collected to assess the psychometric properties of the DTDD. Each sample underwent quality control, missing data analysis, and outlier screening.

Participants

All samples consisted of adult respondents and were collected using an online questionnaire conducted by the Olomouc University Social and Health Institute (OUSHI). The questionnaire batteries included multiple scales, though only a selection of these is analyzed in this article. Participation in the surveys was voluntary, so the respondents could withdraw from the survey at any time. Respondents had to confirm that they had read the informed consent before starting the survey. The questionnaire was completely anonymous. The only more specific data collected was a code combining the type and version of the browser from which the questionnaire was completed. This code is not unique in any way (it is possible to match for multiple respondents and it is not possible to identify the respondent using it) and was used to clean the data for sample 1. The interviewer code was collected for sample 1. It was used to clean the data and to control the collection. A random code was generated for each respondent at

sample 4, which was then used to match the pre-test with the re-test. The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Theology of Palacký University in Olomouc (No. 2020/4). Prior to data analysis, this study was pre-registered in the Open Science Framework [45].

Sample 1. The data collection took place from September 2022 to May 2023 using the snowball method, facilitated by university students as an educational component of their coursework, beyond just a credit requirement. Initially, a sample contained a total of 10518 respondents. To ensure data quality, we removed respondents who did not respond to any DTDD item ($n = 4865$). We also excluded subjects who had a high probability of repeatedly completing the questionnaire ($n = 1335$). This probability was calculated based on the following formula:

$$p = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_{ji} \neq 0}{n}$$

In the given equation, p represents the probability of browser type and version matching for each student, while x_{ji} denotes the number of rows where the i -th element from the interviewer's code column matches the j -th element from the browser's type and version row used to complete the questionnaire; n refers to the total number of rows in the matrix. Subsequently, a tolerance limit was calculated using these match probabilities. In the equation

below, m represents the number of questionnaires completed by the student, and q is the labelling of the student.

$$tolerancelimit = \bar{p} * med(m_1, m_2, m_3 \dots m_k) * \sum_{q=1}^n (q_m > 1)$$

Then we excluded 443 respondents who completed the questionnaire in less than 26 minutes, which was set as the shortest possible time to complete the questionnaire truthfully. This minimum time reflects the fact that the questionnaire batteries included multiple scales beyond those analyzed in this article. Next, we excluded participants who provided identical answers to at least 3 questionnaires used in this study ($n = 205$) and respondents under the age of 18 ($n = 95$). Subsequently, we performed outlier screening based on MAD and excluded $n = 51$ respondents who answered a large number of survey items in the same way. Finally, we excluded $n = 1$ respondents over 80 years old. Thus, the final number of participants was 3523 (Age: $M = 31.14$, $SD = 12.93$, $range = 60$, Females: 65.54%).

Sample 2. The data collection took place from August 2020 to March 2023 using a convenience sample of students from various Czech universities. A sample contained a total of 5333 respondents. We excluded respondents who did not respond to any DTDD item ($n = 3256$), those who completed the questionnaire in less than 15 minutes ($n = 123$), as the questionnaire included multiple scales beyond those analyzed in this article, and respondents under 18 years of

age ($n = 22$). Then, participants who answered a high number of items in the same way ($n = 18$) based on outlier screening were excluded. Finally, we excluded $n = 2$ respondents over 80 years old. The final number of participants was 1912 (Age: $M = 36.67$, $SD = 11.63$, $range = 60$, Females: 80.13%).

Sample 3. The data for this sample was obtained through an online questionnaire that was distributed through a specialist agency (the Czech National Panel). The selection of participants followed a quota sampling approach, aiming to construct a sample that is close to the adult Czech population in terms of age and gender. Potential respondents who are part of the agency's stable panel were contacted online and then rewarded for completing the survey. Data collection was conducted among the Czech population aged 18 to 97 years. The sample included a total of 1665 respondents. To ensure data quality, we used the same procedures as those employed for Sample 2.

We removed respondents who did not respond to any DTDD item ($n = 325$). Next, we excluded those who responded identically to at least 3 of the questionnaires used in this study ($n = 68$). Subsequently, we removed $n = 38$ respondents who answered a large number of survey items in the same way and those who completed the questionnaire in less than 15 minutes ($n = 5$), as the questionnaire included multiple scales beyond those analyzed in this article. Finally, we

excluded $n = 1$ respondents over 80 years old. After excluding poor-quality participants, 1229 respondents remained (Age: $M = 49.8$, $SD = 15.23$, $range = 61$, Females: 43.61%).

Sample 4. For the purposes of test-retest reliability assessment, the data collection was conducted in two waves in January and February 2023 using the convenience sampling method. The time interval between two waves of data collection for the same respondents was set at 14 days, following the model of the [46] validation study. A priori power analysis was conducted to determine the required sample size for assessing test-retest reliability. Optimal number of respondents for test-retest reliability at least 8 subject was calculated in the MBESS package in programming software R. The calculation was performed with the hypothesized value p of 0.79, the number of times each subject is tested (k) 2, at an alpha level of 0.05 with power of 0.80. The sample in the first wave of the collection contained a total of 81 respondents. We excluded 15 of them because these respondents did not complete the items needed to measure the test-retest reliability of the scale. A total of 61 respondents completed the questionnaire at both times. From these participants, we excluded 11 subjects because they completed the retest questionnaire at intervals varying from 14 days. After the exclusion of these poor-quality observations, 50 respondents remained (Age: $M = 32$, $SD = 9$, $range = 47$, Females: 60%).

Socio-demography. Table 1 shows the numbers and percentages of participants in different socio-demographic categories across the four samples. The means and standard

deviations of DTDD scores across demographic categories are depicted in Supplementary

Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the study samples

key	value	Sample 1 (n = 3 523) n(%)	Sample 2 (n = 1 912) n(%)	Sample 3 (n = 1 229) n(%)	Sample 4 (n = 50) n(%)
Gender	1 Man	1214 (34.46%)	380 (19.87%)	693 (56.39%)	20 (40%)
	2 Woman	2309 (65.54%)	1532 (80.13%)	536 (43.61%)	30 (60%)
Economical status	1 Student	1351 (38.35%)	309 (16.16%)	43 (3.5%)	13 (26%)
	2 Non-Working (Excluding Students)	230 (6.53%)	235 (12.29%)	484 (39.38%)	33 (66%)
	3 Working	1942 (55.12%)	1336 (69.87%)	689 (56.06%)	4 (8%)
Education	1 Vocational school and less	543 (15.41%)	119 (6.22%)	521 (42.39%)	3 (6%)
	2 High and Higher vocational school	2033 (57.71%)	824 (43.1%)	416 (33.85%)	22 (44%)
	3 University degree	947 (26.88%)	969 (50.68%)	292 (23.76%)	25 (50%)
Family status	1 Single	1351 (38.35%)	1047 (54.76%)	437 (35.56%)	19 (38%)
	2 In a partner relationship	1253 (35.57%)	635 (33.21%)	204 (16.6%)	12 (24%)
	3 Married	877 (24.89%)	230 (12.03%)	588 (47.84%)	19 (38%)

Measures

The Dark Triad Dirty Dozen (DTDD) was introduced by Jonason and Webster [28] and is one of the tools used to measure the Dark Triad. It measures three malevolent personality traits: Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy. The original instrument contains 12 items rated on a seven-point scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (7). The higher the score, the higher the level of the Dark Triad. The scale underwent a standardised forward-backward translation procedure to ensure semantic and conceptual equivalence between the original English version and the Czech adaptation. Two professional translators with experience in psychological literature were involved in the process. The first translator performed the forward translation from English into Czech, focusing on capturing both the semantic and cultural nuances of the items. The second translator conducted a backward translation of the Czech version back into English. The research team then compared the back-translated English version with the original to identify any inconsistencies or discrepancies. For the purposes of the study, we also used the 14-item version of the DTDD with added items measuring impulsivity (“People often say I’m out of control”) and antisocial behavior (“I like to get revenge on authorities”). These items were obtained from the Czech validation study of the Short Dark Triad (SD3) scale [47]. While these items align with theoretical extensions of the psychopathy subscale, they also present certain conceptual challenges. The impulsivity item was originally designed to reflect erratic lifestyle tendencies in SD3, but in this study, it served as a proxy for

impulsivity as a broader construct. The antisocial behavior item primarily captures vengefulness rather than core rule-breaking tendencies. These nuances should be considered when interpreting the results of the extended DTDD.

The Big Five Inventory (BFI), introduced by Johnem Oliverem P. and Sanjayem Srivastavou [48], is one of the most widely used measures of personality traits and consists of 44 items that measure five personality traits – Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism and Openness. For the purpose of this study, only the Agreeableness, Conscientiousness and Neuroticism factors were used. The Agreeableness subscale consists of 5 positively worded and 4 negatively worded statements and assesses a person's tendency to be pro-social and interpersonally oriented. The Conscientiousness subscale consists of 5 positively worded and 4 negatively worded statements and measures dependability, organisation, and self-control. The Neuroticism subscale consists of 5 positively worded and 3 negatively worded statements and measures the tendency to experience tension and feelings of anxiety. All items consist of statements that are rated on a five-point scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (1) to “strongly agree” (5). Higher scores indicate a higher degree of personality traits. The Czech version used in this study was validated by Hřebíčková and Urbánek [49]. In the present study, the internal consistencies of these scales were as follows: Agreeableness - Cronbach's α : 0.73, 95% CI[0.71-0.74] and McDonald's ω : 0.78; Conscientiousness -Cronbach's α : 0.82, 95%

CI[0.81-0.83] and McDonald's ω : 0.85; Neuroticism - Cronbach's α : 0.87, 95% CI[0.86-0.88] and McDonald's ω : 0.9.

The Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale (RSES), developed by Rosenberg [50], is used to measure individual self-worth. The Czech version used in this study was validated by Blatný and his colleagues [51]. It contains ten self-assessment statements (five positive and five negative) rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from "strongly agree" (1) to "strongly disagree" (4). Higher scores indicate higher self-esteem. In this study, Cronbach's α was 0.85, 95% CI[0.84-0.85] and McDonald's ω : 0.88.

The Toronto Empathy Questionnaire (TEQ) was developed by Spreng and his colleagues [52] and is used to assess the general empathy factor. The Czech version of the questionnaire validated by Novak and his colleagues [53] consists of 7 items rated on a five-point Likert scale ranging from "never" (0) to "always" (4), with higher scores indicating higher empathy. In this study, Cronbach's α was 0.85, 95% CI[0.84-0.85] and McDonald's ω : 0.89.

Health-risk behavior was measured in this study using three items focusing on substance use. The specific wording of the questions is: "How often in the past month have you:" 1. "Smoked", 2. "Drunk alcohol", 3. "Used illegal drugs". Items are rated on a six-point scale from (1) "never" to (6) "many times a day." For the purpose of this study, we summed up the responses to these three questions to create a total score.

Data analysis

The results of the multivariate normality tests showed that multivariate normality was not achieved in either sample. Homoskedasticity was verified using the Breusch-Pagan test. This assumption was violated for samples 2 and 3. Therefore, robust methods were used to test the factor structure in all samples. Missing data analysis showed that the missing values showed no clear pattern in any of the samples used, and therefore, the cases with missing values were removed by the list-wise method.

A confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted on Sample 1 to test the factor structure of the original DTDD scale (12-item version). The same sample was used to test the modified DTDD (14-item version) version with the additional items measuring impulsivity and antisocial behavior. The following models were tested for both versions of the scale: 1) a one-factor model [28]; 2) a two-factor model, where items assessing psychopathy and Machiavellianism were grouped under the single-factor - psychopathy [54, 55]; 3) three-factor structure [28]; 4) hierarchical model [28] and 5) a bifactor model [28, 46]. Based on CFA results from sample 1, we selected the best-fitting model of the original 12-item version of the DTDD and also the best-fitting model of the 14-item version, consisting of new items assessing impulsivity and antisocial behavior. These two models were then tested on Sample 2 and Sample 3 to determine whether either the 12-item version or the 14-item version showed a better fit to the data across different samples.

To assess the adequacy of the correlation matrix for factor analysis, we used the KMO measure and the Bartlett's test. The model fit evaluation included the following indicators: standardised root mean square residual (SRMR), comparative fit index (CFI), Tucker-Lewis index (TLI), and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA). For the RMSEA and SRMR values < 0.08 and < 0.05 , we considered as acceptable or good [56, 57]. CFI and TLI values above 0.95 and 0.97 indicate acceptable or good agreement, respectively [58, 59]. Given the number of response categories in the DTDD scale, it was appropriate to treat the variable as continuous [60, 61] and thus for modelling purposes and use robust maximum likelihood (MLR) estimation.

The internal consistency of the DTDD was assessed using McDonald's ω and Cronbach's α . Values higher than 0.8 for either measure are considered good [62]. The test-retest reliability of the DTDD was explored using the two-way mixed effects intraclass correlation coefficient (sample 4). In line with previous validation studies of the DTDD [46], the time between the two measurements was set at two weeks.

The predictive validity of the original version of the psychopathy subscale and the version containing additional items measuring impulsivity and antisocial behavior was examined in Sample 1 using correlation analysis with health-risk behavior. Consequently, we tested whether a

statistically significant difference exists between versions with and without impulsivity and antisocial behavior items in predicting health risk behavior using Williams' t test [63].

Additionally, the construct validity of the original DTDD scale was evaluated by examining associations with other constructs.

Hypotheses H2, H5, H6, H7 and H8 were tested on Sample 3. Hypothesis H1 was tested on Sample 2. All these hypotheses were tested by linear regressions using robust maximum likelihood estimation while controlling for age and education. Additionally, zero-order correlations (β) for hypotheses H2, H5, H6, H7, and H8 were computed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. Due to the repetition of the variables in each equation, the Bonferroni correction of p-values was performed. Before testing hypothesis H4 on Sample 1, we verified measurement invariance to ensure that the DTDD measures the same constructs in females and males. Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was used to test hypothesis H2. Both analyses - MANOVA and invariance testing - were performed on Sample 1. In hypothesis H3, we tested whether the three-dimensional model adequately fits the data using CFA. H3 was tested on Sample 1, 2 and 3. All statistical analyses were performed in the R programming environment, primarily utilising the following packages: psychtoolbox [64], lavaan [65], papaja [66] and psych [67].

Results

Fit of two versions of the DTDD scale

Bartlett test (Sample 1: $\chi^2 (105) = 27,602.92, p < .001$; Sample 2: $\chi^2 (105) = 12,663.60, p < .001$; Sample 3: $\chi^2 (105) = 10,422.06, p < .001$) as well as KMO (Sample 1: 0.90; Sample 2: 0.87; Sample 3: 0.95) indicated that the DTDD data from samples 1, 2, and 3 were appropriate for the factor analysis. Across the three samples, the one-factor model demonstrated an unsatisfactory fit with the data as measured by both absolute and relative fit indices (Table 2, Supplementary material 2). Although the two-factor model and hierarchical model had a significantly better fit with the data as compared with the one-factor model, absolute and relative fit indices yielded unacceptable values (Table 2, Supplementary material 2). A satisfactory fit with the data was reached by the original three-factor model. Finally, the bifactor model (Table 2, Supplementary material 2) achieved the highest fit with the data model.

Table 2 Fit indices of the tested models (Sample 1, n = 3524)

Tested model	x2	df	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA (90% CI)	p-value
Hierarchic model	881.475	52	0.931	0.912	0.074	0.067 (0.064-0.071)	p < .001
Bifactor model	483.369	42	0.963	0.942	0.035	0.055 (0.051-0.059)	p < .001
Three-factor model	742.781	51	0.942	0.925	0.055	0.062 (0.059-0.066)	p < .001
Two-factor model	2044.872	53	0.834	0.793	0.084	0.103 (0.1-0.107)	p < .001
One-factor model	4503.153	54	0.628	0.546	0.117	0.153 (0.15-0.156)	p < .001

Note. x2 = chi-square, df = degrees of freedom, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, TLI = Tucker-Lewis index, RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval, SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual

All goodness-of-fit metrics indicated that the bifactor model provided a satisfactory fit to the data. However, we decided to use the original three-factor model in subsequent analyses based on both theoretical and empirical considerations. While the bifactor model assumes uncorrelated group factors (narcissism, psychopathy, and Machiavellianism), this contradicts the theoretical framework of the Dark Triad, where these traits are expected to be interrelated [4, 5, 68]. Additionally, bifactor indices further supported this decision. The Explained Common Variance ($ECV = 0.54$), Omega Hierarchical ($\omega_H = 0.54$), and Percentage of Uncontaminated Correlations ($PUC = 0.54$) indicated that although a general Dark Triad factor accounted for a substantial proportion of variance, nearly half of the variance was still explained by the three distinct traits. This suggests that psychopathy, Machiavellianism, and narcissism retain meaningful unique variance beyond their shared antagonistic core. Additionally, the three-factor model demonstrated higher factor loadings for the items (Figure 1), consistent with the original validation study of the DTDD scale [15]. Given these theoretical and empirical justifications, we decided to use the original three-factor model in further analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Factor structure of the three-factor model (Sample 1, $n = 3524$)

Note. M = Machiavellianism, P = Psychopathy, N = Narcissism, DTDD = Dark Triad Dirty Dozen scale items

Comparison of models with and without additional items

In the next step, we added items measuring impulsivity and antisocial behavior to the psychopathy subscale and returned all five models tested in the previous step. The CFA results for all five models in samples 1, 2, and 3 can be found in Supplementary Table 3. Then we compared the three-factor and bifactor model of the original (12 items) DTDD scale with the three-factor and bifactor model with additional items (14 items).

Although the 14-item version fits the data satisfactorily, the 12-version model fits the data better (Table 3). Taken together, the 12-item version had the best ability to explain the data; therefore, we continued with the original 12-item model in further analyses.

Table 3 Fit indices of the tested models (Sample 1, n = 3524)

Tested model	χ^2	df	CFI	TLI	SRMR	RMSEA (90% CI)	p-value
Three-factor model 12-items	742.781	51	0.942	0.925	0.055	0.062 (0.059-0.066)	p < .001
Three-factor model 14-items	1210.545	74	0.916	0.897	0.063	0.066 (0.063-0.069)	p < .001
Bifactor model 12-items	483.369	42	0.963	0.942	0.035	0.055 (0.051-0.059)	p < .001
Bifactor model 14-items	1431.356	64	0.9	0.857	0.109	0.078 (0.075-0.081)	p < .001

Note. χ^2 = chi-square, df = degrees of freedom, CFI = Comparative Fit Index, TLI = Tucker-Lewis index, RMSEA = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation, CI = Confidence Interval, SRMR = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual

We inspected Bollen residual correlations for the 14-item model in Sample 1 (Supplementary Table 4). The added impulsivity item showed higher residuals with DTDD_4n ($r_{\text{resid}} = .136$) and, to a lesser extent, with DTDD_2n ($r_{\text{resid}} = .079$). The added antisocial item also showed a clear residual with DTDD_4n ($r_{\text{resid}} = .231$). This pattern aligns with the weaker global fit of the 14-item model and suggests overlap between the added items and narcissism. Internal consistency and test-retest reliability

The test-retest results showed a high degree of consistency of responses between the two repeated measurements with a coefficient value of 0.83, 95% CI[0.71-0.9], $p < 0.001$. The results

of Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega for all samples are depicted in the Table 4 below. For the original 12-item version of the scale, Cronbach's alpha ranged between 0.81-0.89 and Omega ranged between 0.86-0.91 across all samples.

Table 4 Cronbach's Alpha and McDonald's Omega coefficients of the original 12 item version of the DTDD scale

Sample	Alfa 12 item version	CI	Omega 12 item version	CI
1	0.85	[0.84-0.85]	0.89	[0.84-0.86]
2	0.81	[0.8-0.82]	0.86	[0.8-0.83]
3	0.89	[0.88-0.89]	0.91	[0.88-0.9]

Note. CI = Confidence Interval

Measurement Invariance and differences between males and females in DTDD

In examining the measurement invariance of the three-factor model, we tested configural, metric, scalar, and strict invariance to determine whether the DTDD scale functions equivalently across genders. We observed only marginal differences in the measurement (Supplementary Table 5), characterised by $\Delta CFI < 0.01$ and $\Delta RMSEA < 0.015$. This implies that the DTDD scale equally captures dark personality traits in both females and males, indicating that any observed differences in scores reflect true differences in trait levels rather than measurement bias. MANOVA results showed a statistically significant effect of gender on the combined dependent variables, Pillai's Trace = 0.0716, $F(3, 3519) = 90.49$, $p < .001$. This means that while the DTDD

measures the constructs equivalently across genders, the results indicate that men and women systematically differ in their levels of narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy.

Predictive validity testing of the psychopathy subscale

The results revealed that the psychopathy subscale with additional items showed a slightly stronger correlation with health risk behaviors ($r = 0.17, p < 0.001$) compared to the 4-item original subscale ($r = 0.11, p < 0.001$). Additionally, these two correlations were found to be statistically different from each other ($t = -7.7354, df = 3521, p < 0.001$). The analysis provided evidence supporting a slightly improved prediction of the psychopathy subscale with additional items in predicting health risk behaviors compared to the 4-item original subscale. However, the difference in correlation due to sample size does not provide a convincing predictive advantage. Moreover, given the better fit of the three-factor model of the original 12-item version and the fact that impulsivity is not a core feature of psychopathy, we continued with the original 12-item version in further analyses.

To better understand the contribution of the additional items, we conducted follow-up analyses comparing the predictive validity of different variations of the psychopathy subscale. When testing specific items, the 5-item psychopathy subscale that included only the erratic lifestyle/impulsivity item ($r = 0.16, p < 0.001$) demonstrated a significantly stronger association with health risk behaviors compared to the original 4-item psychopathy subscale ($r = 0.11, p < 0.001$), and this difference was statistically significant ($t = -8.0792, df = 3521, p < 0.001$). The 5-item version including only the antisocial behavior item also showed a numerically higher correlation ($r = 0.12, p < 0.001$) than the 4-item subscale ($r = 0.11, p < 0.001$), although the effect was small ($t = -2.4410, df = 3521, p = 0.0073$). Crucially, a direct comparison of the 6-item score

(impulsivity + antisocial behavior) with the 5-item impulsivity-only score using Steiger's test for dependent correlations showed no meaningful difference ($r = 0.1627$ vs. 0.1593 ; Steiger's $z = -0.99$, $p = 0.324$), indicating that the incremental contribution of the antisocial item beyond impulsivity is negligible. Overall, the pattern suggests that the observed improvement from the 4- to the 6-item score is driven primarily by the impulsivity item, while differences remain small.

Associations of DTDD Traits with Personality Dimensions

Table 5 below shows the results of the regression equations used to test our remaining hypotheses. Even after correcting p-values for multiple testing, all the associations were statistically significant (except for the connection between empathy and narcissism, where the association was not significant even before correction).

Table 5 Results of regression analyses (Sample 2, $n = 1912$; Sample 3, $n = 1229$)

Predictor	Standardized β coefficient	Zero-order correlations	Outcome variable
Narcissism	-0.06*	-0.1***	Self-esteem
Neuroticism	0.12***	0.11***	Machiavellianism
Neuroticism	0.12***	0.11***	Narcissism
Agreeableness	-0.39***	-0.43***	Psychopathy
Agreeableness	-0.38***	-0.42***	Machiavellianism
Agreeableness	-0.23***	-0.26***	Narcissism
Conscientiousness	-0.22***	-0.24***	Psychopathy
Conscientiousness	-0.23***	-0.25***	Machiavellianism
Conscientiousness	-0.12***	-0.12***	Narcissism
Narcissism	-0.03	-0.08**	Empathy
Machiavellianism	-0.16***	-0.23***	Empathy
Psychopathy	-0.30***	-0.35***	Empathy

Note. Standard errors in all regressions were between 0.02 and 0.03; * = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$

Regression analysis indicates a slight negative link between self-esteem and narcissism.

Neuroticism is positively associated with Machiavellianism and narcissism. At the same time, all components of the Dark Triad are negatively associated with Agreeableness and

Conscientiousness. Negative relationships were found between empathy and both psychopathy and Machiavellianism, while narcissism did not show a significant association with empathy.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to examine the psychometric properties of the Czech version of the Dark Triad Dirty Dozen Scale. Our results supported the original three-factor structure of the 12-item version of the DTDD. Testing the 14-item version of the DTDD revealed that it predicted health risk behaviors better, however, it had a lower model fit as compared with the original 12-item version. We found the DTDD to be measurement invariant in terms of gender, although a higher mean score in narcissism, psychopathy, and Machiavellianism was observed in males. All Dark Triad traits were negatively associated with Agreeableness and Conscientiousness. All Dark Triad traits demonstrated a statistically significant positive relationship with Neuroticism, though the magnitude of the standardised correlation coefficient was notably small. Finally, empathy was negatively related to psychopathy and Machiavellianism, while self-esteem showed a weak negative association with Narcissism.

The results of the CFA in our study confirmed that the original three-factor model had satisfactory fit with the data and showed the highest factor-item loading. This finding was consistent with the results of the original validation study of the DTDD scale [28], which suggested that the three-factor was the most optimal. These findings, however, contradict several studies [46, 69, 70] that proposed a bi-factor structure. While a bifactor model has been shown to work well in some studies it may not be universally applicable. There are theoretical and empirical reasons why we preferred the three-factor structure to the bifactor. The bifactor model assumes uncorrelated group factors (narcissism, psychopathy, and Machiavellianism) and a single general factor (the Dark Triad) [71]. However, according to the theoretical framework of the Dark Triad, these traits are expected to be interrelated [4, 5, 68]. Additionally, bifactor models may overfit the data, as evidenced by simulation study [72]. Thus, while a bifactor model

may provide a good fit in certain contexts, our findings support the three-factor model as a more theoretically consistent solution for the DTDD in a general population sample.

In our study, we investigated the factor structure of the 14-item model, including an additional two items each measuring impulsivity and antisocial behavior. While these characteristics are often associated with psychopathy in both theoretical models and empirical studies [15, 27, 29], their inclusion in the psychopathy subscale of the DTDD requires careful consideration. Although impulsivity and antisocial behavior are associated with psychopathy, they are considered peripheral rather than core features of the construct in some psychopathy models [13, 14].

Our findings showed that the original three-factor 12-item model of the DTDD scale showed a significantly better fit to our data compared to the extended 14-item model. An examination of the residual correlations revealed that the added impulsivity item exhibits relatively higher residual correlations with two items measuring narcissism. This pattern may suggest shared variance between impulsivity and narcissism, which aligns with previous research indicating that narcissistic individuals tend to exhibit functional impulsivity, characterized by venturesome social engagement rather than poor self-regulation [73, 74]. However, these residual correlations also indicate that the added item does not function independently within the model as intended, potentially confounding the distinct measurement of impulsivity. Given this, along with the superior fit of the original model, we opted to retain the 12-item structure.

However, the psychopathy subscale with the added items assessing impulsivity and antisocial behavior (6 items) showed a slightly stronger correlation with health risk behaviors than psychopathy measured by the original DTDD scale (4 items). While this suggests that the inclusion of impulsivity may provide some additional predictive insight, the observed correlation

(.17) remains weak and explains less than 3% of the variance in health-risk behaviors. These findings may be partially explained by research [75] suggesting that specific facets of psychopathy, such as the lifestyle facet, are associated with impulsivity-related traits like sensation seeking, which could influence certain health-risk behaviors. Moreover, the variable measuring health-risk behaviors was limited to capturing only the frequency of nicotine, alcohol, and illegal drug use, which may not fully capture the breadth of health-risk behaviors. Further, the residual correlations revealed that the added impulsivity item exhibited relatively strong correlations with narcissism-related items, suggesting conceptual overlap. Given these residual correlations and the poorer model fit, our results support the argument that impulsivity may not function as an independent component within the DTDD psychopathy subscale. This is consistent with perspectives suggesting that impulsivity is not a core defining feature of psychopathy but rather a peripheral trait [20]. We also found that the three-factor model of the DTDD is invariant between genders. This indicates the DTDD assesses males and females equivalently, reflecting the same underlying traits regardless of gender. As in previous studies [76, 77], we conclude that males score higher than females in the Dark Triad, the biggest difference was found in Narcissism. Drawing from [78] biosocial construction model, this gender difference can be attributed to traditional societal roles, where agentic traits, often associated with the Dark Triad [79], are deemed more acceptable in males due to their historical access to wealth-generating activities. Jonason and Davis [80] also demonstrated that gender differences in Dark Triad scoring may be mediated by such gender role differences. Another perspective on gender differences in Dark Triad scores is provided by life history theory. This theory suggests that men and women adopt different reproductive strategies, with men more likely to pursue fast life history strategies, focusing on frequent mating and lower parental investment, while women tend to prioritize slower strategies with greater emphasis on caregiving. Since Dark Triad traits align

more closely with fast life history strategies, it is more likely for these traits to manifest in men than in women [68, 69]. The evolutionary framework [83] may offer other perspectives on how to view the difference in Dark Triad score levels.

Next, we examined the relationships between Dark Triad traits and selected Big Five traits. Conscientiousness was negatively associated with psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism, a finding also observed by Paulhus and Williams [21] and more recently by Savard and his colleagues [84]. Thus, the hypothesis H7 of a negative relationship between Conscientiousness and all traits of the Dark Triad has been confirmed. This aligns with theoretical frameworks that suggest low Conscientiousness reflects traits like poor self control, recklessness, and deficits in avoidance orientation [85] - attributes closely tied especially to the lifestyle/antisocial factor in psychopathy [13, 14, 31]. This stands in contrast to the findings of Kowalski and his colleagues [23], who did not observe a significant relationship between narcissism and any of the Big Five traits at a broader level. In our findings, we further confirmed hypothesis H6. There are significant negative associations between all traits of the Dark Triad and Agreeableness, consistent with previous studies [25, 86]. Agreeableness reflects interpersonal traits such as trust, cooperation, and altruism, which are inherently opposed to the manipulative and antagonistic nature of the Dark Triad traits. To shed light on this, a recent study emphasised a pronounced correlation between the “dark personality factor” and Agreeableness. While this shared core of dark personality traits extends beyond mere low Agreeableness, it serves as a pivotal connection among the traits of psychopathy, narcissism, and Machiavellianism [87]. The original formulation of Hypothesis H2, that psychopathy and Machiavellianism are related to neuroticism, was non-directional and lacked specificity in predicting the nature of these associations. This limitation highlights the importance of formulating hypotheses that are theoretically grounded and meaningfully testable. Our results suggested a positive relationship

between neuroticism and Machiavellianism, as well as between neuroticism and narcissism. Neuroticism is characterized by emotional instability, heightened sensitivity to stress, and a tendency toward negative affect. A recent study [88] highlights that, despite its association with emotional detachment, Machiavellianism correlates with neuroticism, suggesting a more complex interplay between manipulative tendencies and emotional distress. Similarly, vulnerable narcissism has been consistently associated with neuroticism, negative affectivity, and anxious temperament [88].

Subsequently, we tested the relationship between narcissism and self-esteem. The results of the regression analysis indicated a weak negative relationship. Hypothesis H1 hypothesized a positive relationship between narcissism and self-esteem; therefore, the results did not support it. These findings raise an important question regarding the conceptualization of narcissism in this study. The hypothesis that narcissism would be positively correlated with self-esteem was based on the broader assumption that narcissistic traits involve an elevated view of the self. However, the use of the DTDD measure instead of the SD3 measure may have influenced the direction of this relationship. As originally reported by Jonason and Webster [28] and subsequently confirmed by other studies [89–91], DTDD-narcissism tends to capture the more vulnerable aspects of the trait that are negatively associated with self-esteem. In contrast, SD3-narcissism primarily reflects grandiose aspects [23, 89] that are more consistently associated with higher self-esteem. Given that this study was based on DTDD, the weak negative relationship between narcissism and self-esteem is consistent with previous research and suggests that the vulnerable components of narcissism in DTDD may be more influential in this context. Moreover, the formulation of hypothesis H1 did not explicitly account for these differences between different operationalisations of narcissism. This oversight points to the need for greater precision in linking theoretical expectations to specific measurement instruments. Finally, a negative relationship

between empathy was found for psychopathy and Machiavellianism, with a stronger negative relationship for the psychopathy trait, consistent with a number of studies [92, 93]. These results confirmed hypothesis H8. This observed negative correlation between psychopathy and empathy can be elucidated by understanding that one of the defining characteristics of psychopathic traits is a diminished empathic response to the suffering of others. Neurobiological models, such as the Integrated Emotion Systems (IES) model [94, 95], provide insight into these deficits by emphasizing the role of the amygdala and ventro-medial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC). The amygdala plays a critical role in stimulus-reinforcement learning, such as aversive conditioning, which is often impaired in individuals with psychopathy [94]. This dysfunction contributes to reduced sensitivity to aversive feedback, including distress signals such as fear, sadness, or pain expressed by others [95].

Strengths and Limitations

One of the strengths of our study is the number of samples. This allowed us to verify the CFA results on samples collected at different times from different populations, which contributes to the robustness of the results. An important contribution of the paper is also the examination of the predictive validity of the DTDD measure in relation to health risk behavior. Also, this study was preregistered, and the results can be easily and fully replicated due to the publicly available data and code.

Regarding the limitations of the study, it is possible that some of the relationships examined were influenced by other factors that were not identified and examined in the study, and therefore some of the expected relationships were not confirmed. However, we believe that our measurement tool accurately represents the intended constructs, as the resulting three-dimensional model satisfactorily explains the correlations among individual DTDD items, and

many anticipated associations were indeed confirmed. Additionally, the formulation of Hypothesis H2 lacked directional specificity, making it insufficiently precise for meaningful testing. Similarly, Hypothesis H1 was based on an overly broad assumption about narcissism and self-esteem, without considering differences between DTDD and SD3 measures. These issues underscore the importance of theoretical clarity and careful alignment between hypotheses and measurement tools to ensure valid interpretations of results. The original pre-registration also included the hypothesis “DTDD composite score is positively associated with narcissism, Machiavellianism, and psychopathy.” This hypothesis was removed during the review process due to its tautological nature, which reflects a weakness in the original study design. Finally, the health risk behavior items used to test the predictive validity may not be sensitive enough to capture all aspects of health risk behavior. In addition, this variable may have been influenced by respondents’ willingness to answer sensitive questions honestly, although the collection was completely anonymous.

A further limitation of our study relates to sample 1, where there is the possibility of repeated completion of the questionnaire. This stems from the fact that respondents were recruited by students during their practical training, leading to the possibility that some participants may have been approached more than once. To address this concern, we designed a formula, detailed in the methods section, to identify and then exclude any suspected duplicates from the analysis.

Implications

The findings of this study contribute to the validation of the Czech version of the DTDD scale, supporting its psychometric robustness. The original 12-item three-factor model demonstrated satisfactory fit across samples, measurement invariance between genders, and consistent associations with external variables grounded in established theoretical frameworks. These results confirm the utility of the DTDD for assessing dark personality traits in the Czech context. Also the findings of this study can serve as a basis for further research on the relationships between dark personality traits and various aspects of mental health and well-being. Our results demonstrated that the 7-item psychopathy subscale showed improved predictive ability for health-risk behaviors compared to the 4-item version. This aspect of the study has implementation in both follow-up research and practice: further research is needed to test the ability of the DTDD scale to reliably predict health risk behaviors. Future research could expand on these findings by exploring the scale's predictive validity in broader contexts and its applicability to diverse populations. The validated DTDD scale can serve as a reliable tool in psychological practice, aiding in the assessment of dark personality traits in clinical, organizational, and research settings.

Conclusions

Considering our study's overall findings, we recommend using the original 12-item version of the DTDD scale, which demonstrated superior model fit and theoretical consistency. Our study highlights the importance of maintaining conceptual clarity in psychometric instruments. The validated Czech version of the DTDD provides a valuable addition to the arsenal of psychological tools, enabling researchers and practitioners to reliably assess dark personality traits in the Czech-speaking population. Declaration.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Theology of Palacký University in Olomouc (No. 2020/4). Informed consent was provided to all study participants, they were informed of their rights and agreed to participate in the study.

Consent for publication

Consent for publication does not apply to this manuscript.

Competing interests

All authors agree to the final form of the article. All authors of the article declare that they have no existing or potential conflicts of interest that could affect the results and conclusions presented in the article.

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Availability of data and materials

The datasets that were generated and analysed during the study are available in the Open Science Framework (<https://osf.io/8dp72/files/osfstorage>) repository. The DTDD scale translated into Czech is available in supplementary material 6, and the list of abbreviations used is available in supplementary material 7.

Authors' contributions

The authors made the following contributions. Kristyna Zivna: Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft Preparation, Writing - Review & Editing, Formal analysis, Data curation; Lukas Novak: Writing - Review & Editing, Writing - Original Draft Preparation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Supervision; Radka Zidkova: Writing - Review & Editing; Jakub Helvich: Writing - Review & Editing; Peter Tavel: Writing - Review & Editing, Resources, Funding acquisition; Klara Malinakova: Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

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